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How To Write a Podcast Script

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Select Your Audience and Topic

Choose a topic or theme for your podcast episode to get started. Think about your personal interests and what your target audience could find interesting and useful.

Research

Research your topic to acquire facts, figures, stories, and examples before you begin writing. Organize into an outline that will act as the script's framework.

Develop a Captivating Hook

Start your podcast with an attention-grabbing hook to draw listeners in. This can be a provocative question, a fascinating fact, a true anecdote, or a sneak peek at what the episode will contain.

Give a brief overview of your podcast and yourself. Give your name, your area of expertise (if applicable), and a brief synopsis of what the episode will cover to the listeners.

Section the Content

To keep the episode organized and to help you arrange your thoughts, divide your content into sections or pieces. Each section needs to serve a distinct purpose and add to the broader story.

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Write in Conversation

The tone of podcasts is often friendlier than that of academic writing. Write in a way that, when said aloud, seems natural. Do not use jargon or excessively sophisticated language as this may turn off your readers.

Use key phrases or bullet points

Use bullet points or key phrases to outline your points for each section rather than writing lengthy paragraphs. As a result, it is simpler to keep the dialogue flowing when recording.

Add Transitions

To transition between sections or themes naturally, use transitional words and sentences. Transitions assist keep the episode cohesive and lead your audience through it.

Use Personal Narratives and Examples

Your podcast can become more relatable and interesting by include personal anecdotes, stories, and examples from real life. They support your arguments and maintain listeners' interest.

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Some additional guidelines

Students will create/record individual, pair or group podcasts and they will be working individually or in pairs/groups (both during script preparation and during podcast creation).

Podcast need to be grounded in theory (at least to some extent). A short explanation of the theoretical background can be found below the guidelines. It is important that some basic theoretical concepts be introduced through the podcast, such as accent discrimination, accentism, accent bias, language discrimination, linguicism, language bias, languagism, glottophobia, linguistic profiling and others.

Students will talk about accent discrimination in general, accent discrimination in L1 and accent discrimination towards non-native speakers of English. Students should focus on accentism in education, but could also discuss accentism in the media, on social media. Students can recount their own or someone else's personal stories.

Theoretical background – the description of accenti discrimination in the project proposal:

Discrimination can take different forms, and language-related discrimination is among the most insidious. Language is a personal attribute, but also reveals much about an individual's ethnic background, gender, sexual orientation, or socioeconomic status. If left

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unchecked, discrimination related to linguistic issues can thus seriously affect not only the life outcomes of individuals but also broader social dynamics amongst groups.

Non-standard speakers, or speakers with ethnic backgrounds, may experience different forms of linguistic microaggressions and accent discrimination, such that they may be perceived as incomprehensible, mocked and shamed for how they speak, or become the object of normative comments that address their pronunciation (Corona & Block, 2020; Dovchin, 2020). These forms of discrimination are usually experienced in school, and linguistic discrimination can be one of the main causes of students' school failure and early school leaving. In this respect, the podcast aims at raising awareness on issues linked to linguistic discrimination in order to promote the inclusion of speakers with different linguistic backgrounds in education.

The school environment is a hotspot for addressing accentism: students are exposed to different accents and form and reinforce attitudes towards them on the basis of peer pressure; teachers are confronted daily with regional and non-native accents of the national language, and are at risk of unconsciously succumbing to prejudice and negative evaluations of non-standard varieties. The new superdiversity of contemporary European societies requires teachers to be better equipped with the knowledge, skills and competencies needed to prepare students to live in increasingly multicultural settings. Conscious and unconscious linguistic discrimination on

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teachers' part can lead students from marginalised (linguistic) backgrounds to be judged more negatively in terms of academic achievement.

Such attitudes may be based on the assumption that people with a nonstandard accent are not proficient or sufficiently fluent in the language, regardless of their general linguistic competence; a nonstandard accent may also be interpreted as a lack of willingness to master the standard language, especially in the case of speakers from immigrant backgrounds (Boyd, 2003). Such assumptions can lead pupils to feel less valued and discourage them from putting effort into their studies, which may, in turn, become a self-fulfilling prophecy (Dovidio, 2010);

Accent deprecation and discrimination also plays an important role in the foreign language classroom, particularly in English language education. Foreign language curricula typically emphasise intercultural communicative competence as the underlying goal of teaching and learning. This curricular goal, however, often contrasts with a classroom reality in which only standard British and standard American English are held in high esteem whereas other accents are perceived as less appropriate, less correct, or less educated - to the extent that some may even be associated with strong stereotypes and negative social and cultural meanings (Carrie, 2017; Forsberg et al., 2019; Henderson et al., 2012; Hartmann, 2021; Kruse, 2016; Ladegaard & Sachdev, 2006; McKenzie & Gilmore, 2017; Meer, 2021; Meer et al., 2021a,b; Vettorel, 2018). The podcasts will contrast such

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tendencies by promoting an inclusive approach both to English as a lingua franca and other vernacular languages in the European context.

Interesting fact: Among the various members of the EU, France is the only country that has actually discussed the implementation of a specific legal device against languagebased discrimination. The law, which has been adopted in the French parliament in November 2020, primarily relies on inputs provided by academic scholars, most of whom were linguists. However, in the remaining EU countries, there appears to be a lack of interest in the topic of linguistic discrimination.

Some interesting links:

<https://www.listennotes.com/podcasts/the-influency/44-accent-bias-r87zBC2De9-/>

<https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2022/jun/12/accent-discrimination-is-alive-and-kicking-in-britain-study-suggests>

Some research studies to be looked into for the theoretical overview of the topic:

Alzahrani, R.A. (2023). Attitudes Toward Saudi English: Decentering the Inner-Circle. *Journal of Psycholinguist Research*, 52, 809–829.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-022-09925-0>

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Carrie, E. (2017). 'British is professional, American is urban': Attitudes towards English reference accents in Spain. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics* 272, doi:10.1111/ijal.12139

Davydova, J. (2015). A study in the perception of native and non-native Englishes by German learners. *Journal of Linguistics and Language Teaching*, 6(1), 89–117.

Dragojevic, M. & Goatley-Soan, S. (2020). Americans' attitudes toward foreign accents: evaluative hierarchies and underlying processes. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*. DOI: 10.1080/01434632.2020.1735402

Garrett, P. 2010. *Attitudes to Language*. CUP

Meer, P., Hartmann, J., & Rumlich, D. (2021). Attitudes of German high school students toward different varieties of English. *Applied Linguistics*, 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amab046>

Meer, P., Hartmann, J. & Rumlich, D. (2021). Folklinguistic perceptions of Global Englishes among German learners of English. *European Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 9(2), 391-416. <https://doi.org/10.1515/eujal-2020-0014>

Tan, Y. Y., & C. Castelli. 2013. "Intelligibility and Attitudes: How American English and Singapore English are Perceived around the World." *English World-Wide* 34 (2): 177–201. doi:10.1075/eww.34.2.03tan.

Yook, C. & Lindemann, S. (2012). The role of speaker identification in Korean university students' attitudes towards five varieties of English. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 34(3), 279-296. DOI:10.1080/01434632.2012.734509

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Podcast Script Structure

1. **Show Introduction**
2. **Topic Introduction**
3. **Guest Introduction**
4. **Questions for the guest**
5. **Bullet points with the most interesting details**
6. **Thank you notes, and outro**